

PLANINNG AND ENGAGEMENT ARENAS FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY LANDSCAPES

PEARLS

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Abstract:

Deliverable 2.3 entitled Research Seminar corresponds to WP 2 SUSTAINABLE IMPLEMENTATION: POLICIES AND PRACTICES led by the University of Seville and Ben-Gurion. This Deliverable collects the content of this activity that has been carried out in the Faculty of Geography and History of the University of Seville on 25 and 26 October 2022. These has been enabling dissemination of the PEARLS project's objective, findings, and deliverables to wider audiences by the host institution. To reach this, the Research Seminar has been incorporated into the Doctoral Program in Geography of the International Doctoral School of the University of Seville.

The Deliverable collects the content of the presentations made by the three lecturers during the first day of the seminar as well as the field trip made on the second day to the thermos-solar plants Valle 1 and Valle 2 in the municipality of San José del Valle, in Cádiz. To strengthen the relationships between the participants, a networking event was also organized for those attending the seminar who are part of the PEARLS project.

Index:

I.	Introduction	5
II.	Research Seminar organization and contents	5
III.	Research Seminar lectures	7
IV.	Networking Event.....	43
V.	Field work on local case Study.....	44
VI.	References.....	46
VII.	PEARLS Consortium.....	47

I. Introduction

This deliverable contains the fourth task to WP 2 SUSTAINABLE IMPLEMENTATION: POLICIES AND PRACTICES. The WP objectives were formulated in i) the framework to examine and compare national energy policy, land use planning and landscape practice schemes; ii) to analyze environmental impact assessment procedures to enable the inclusion of natural and cultural aspects to construct a return mechanism for policy makers; and iii) to research and develop tools to increase public participation in energy policy and renewable energy landscape implementation practices. To put the three of them in value, WP2 includes research and training together with support for dissemination by WP1. The idea is to facilitate and disseminate a better understanding of legal frameworks and daily practice in the implementation of REL within PhD students.

The WP tasks comprise Research Reports (D.2.1.) from participating countries following a common scheme. These reports have been establishing by the national contexts frameworks for the construction of comparative energy policy, land use planning and landscape practice. The second task consists of deep interviews with national/regional policy makers and technicians to obtain direct information about the public participation system in renewable energies implementation. The final task will consist of three types of outputs: a) to analyse environmental impact assessment procedures to enable the inclusion of natural and cultural aspects; b) to construct a return mechanism for policy makers; and c) fieldwork on real EIA specific cases. All these outputs allow WP2 participants to prepare two co-authored papers on energy policy and REL spatial planning and b) to organise a Research Seminar for PhD Students.

The Research Seminar has been held by the University of Seville together with Ben Gurion University last 26 and 27 October 2022. The Seminar has consisted in two daily sessions of lectures and fieldwork. A networking event has been held in between to reinforce PEARLS project capacity to facilitate knowledge sharing through secondments experiences. Due to the international approach of this activity, the Seminar has been co-founded to the Doctoral Programme in Geography from the University of Seville. The total amount of participants has been 37 people within PhD students (12), PEARLS secondments and local participants (25).

II. Research Seminar organization and contents

This Research Seminar has been organised by the University of Seville. The objective pursued has been both to fulfil the WP2 task agenda resulting from the research carried out throughout the project and to prepare this deliverable. To achieve this, it was essential to have the participation of those members of the project who were able to offer relevant results while opening their dissemination to a wider public. The initial idea of organising an activity for PhD students participating in PEARLS as secondments gave way to other secondments from the non-academic sector as well as to PhD students from the University of Seville who are not involved in the PEARLS project to date. This proposal fits perfectly into the Geography PhD Programme of the University of Seville. Hence the proposal to organise this Research Seminar as part of this programme.

The Doctoral Programme in Geography of the University of Seville is part of the R&D&I framework of the scientific-professional sector of Geography through several research teams recognised for their national and international prestige. Some members of these teams bring to the programme outstanding management experience in the public administration and the

business world, in areas as relevant as planning, land management, regional development and R&D&I. The lecturers who make up the Programme have been developing various competitive projects and contracts with a high level of initiative and scientific capacity in their commitment to R&D&I, which is the essence of its operation. Particularly noteworthy is the diversity of national and international centres/universities with which collaboration agreements, contracts, or incentive agreements (public and private) have been signed at regional, national, and international level. In addition, its involvement in the Strategic Plan of the University of Seville incorporates an important stimulus to research and innovative experiences in its international projection and in the production and transfer of knowledge.

Due to the importance given to internationalisation, the Research Seminar for PhD students on "Renewable Energy Landscapes and Spatial Planning: A Transnational Mediterranean" was submitted to the call for training activities of the International Doctoral School of the University of Seville. The activity was approved, which has allowed its academic insertion in the PhD Programme in Geography, widening the number of potential participants, and achieving co-funding of the expenses. Therefore, the activity has been offered to students of the Doctoral Programme in Geography from Albania, Chile, Ecuador, Iran, Morocco, and Spain. In addition, PhD students of the PEARLS project from Israel, Italy, and Portugal, as well as Spain, and secondments have attended. To achieve this, the seminar has been online for those who were outside Europe.

To reinforce the visibility of the PEARLS Project the Seminar has been renamed Planning and Engagement Arenas for Renewable Energy Landscapes. The contents of the Seminar correspond to the research results of the project and reinforce the regional component through the presentation of a case study.

The structure of the Seminar comprises

1. Three theoretical sessions given by the members of the project.

Speaker: Na'ama Teschner. Assistant Professor at the Department of Geography and Environmental Development of the Ben Gurion University in Israel and the head of external relations committee at the School of Sustainability and Climate Change (SSCC)

Speaker: Eva Loukogeorgaki. Associate Professor of Marine Structures in the Civil Engineering Department of Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH)

Speaker: Vasiliki (Betty) Charalampopoulou. President & CEO of GEOSYSTEMS HELLAS S.A.

2. A field trip to the solar thermal power plants Valle 1 and Valle 2 in San José del Valle, Cádiz, 120 km southeast of Seville <https://www.energy.sener/project/valle-1-and-valle-2-plant>

Speaker: Mr. Ignacio Grimaldi from SENER Group <https://www.group.sener/>

Research Seminar – Seminario de Doctorado - Doctoral Programme on Geography – University of Seville – PEARLS Project - Research Seminar – Seminario de Doctorado

PLANNING AND ENGAGEMENT ARENAS FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY LANDSCAPES IN SOUTHERN EUROPEAN COUNTRIES & ISRAEL

26 October 2022

16:00 to 20:00 Open lectures Aula X – Faculty of Geography and History, University of Seville

[16:00-17:30] *A place under the sun: planning, landscape, and participation in a case of a solar powerplant in the Israeli desert.*
Naama Teschner Department of Geography and Environmental Development - Ben-Gurion University of the Negev (Israel)

[17:30-17:50] Coffee Break

[17:50-19:15] *GIS-based multi-criteria decision analysis for renewable energy systems' site selection*
Eva Loukogeorgaki Department of Civil Engineering - Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece)

[19:15-20:00] *Transition from research to operations, use of Downstream Space Technologies to ensure nature and climate-positive action*
Betty Charalampopoulou President and CEO in GEOSYSTEMS HELLAS - Athens (Greece)

27 October 2022

16:00 to 20:00 Fieldwork to thermo-solar plants Valle 1 & 2 San José del Valle (Cádiz)

PEARLS Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Grant Agreement No 78039

A networking event has taken place between the two activities. The aim was to find a common meeting place in which to strengthen the cohesion of the PEARLS project participants who took part in the Seminar. In this way, information on the day-to-day running of the project was shared by participants from the academic and non-academic sectors and to encourage the incorporation of new secondments as part of the exchange of knowledge, work schemes and training experiences.

III. Research Seminar lectures

A place under the sun: Planning, landscape, and participation in a case of a solar powerplant in the Israeli desert, by Na'ama Teschner

This research shows how perceived landscape impacts influence public willingness to accept changes in the landscape. The connection between the effectiveness of LA procedures vis-à-vis the inclusion of the public in decision-making related to RES siting has received less attention. Speaker examines the role of LAs in planning via the eyes of policymakers and experts and evaluate the capacity of current tools to influence the process. Additionally, the role (or lack thereof) of the public in LAs is presented. Our unique case—one of the largest in the world thermo-solar “tower” plant, located near a small desert village—exemplifies the place for landscape consideration in national-level mega-infrastructure. Based on documents analysis and semi-structured interviews, the findings demonstrate the struggle between competing goals such as financial and temporal efficiency, RES targets, landscape protection, and public participation. Despite independent efforts to promote the latter two, there may be little connection between the assessment of landscape effects and public participation because there is no mechanism for post-evaluation of a project’s impacts, and any debates on the actual effects remain theoretical. Second, that landscape impacts of large-scale infrastructure can mainly be avoided in the stage of site location, and at this stage, the room for public input remains limited.

A PLACE UNDER THE SUN:

PLANNING, LANDSCAPE AND PARTICIPATION IN A CASE OF A SOLAR POWERPLANT IN THE ISRAELI DESERT

Na'ama Teschner

אוניברסיטת בן-גוריון בנגב
Ben-Gurion University of the Negev
جامعة بن-غوريون في النقب

Research seminar, Seville, 27/10/2022

Article

A Place under the Sun: Planning, Landscape and Participation in a Case of a Solar Powerplant in the Israeli Desert

Ela Romov and Na'ama Teschner

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www.pearlsproject.org

http://www.heightsourceenergy.com/image-gallery/#_WmmwK5liWbM4

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What is the role of LA in planning processes of RES?
 - // To what extent do current tools (EIA, LIA) can influence siting and design processes for RES projects?
1. How do planners and decision-makers perceive the role (or lack thereof) of residents and the general public in LAs, during the plan's appraisal and approval stages?

OUTLINE

- **Introduction:**
 - Climate change and renewable energies: global
 - Solar energy: impacts and trade-offs
 - Social acceptance and public participation
- **Landscape Impact Assessment: definitions, tools, limitations**
- **Case-study:**
 - Background: Israel's energy geographies
 - Planning, landscape and participation in *Ashalim* thermo-solar project
- **Conclusions**

INTRODUCTION: CLIMATE CHANGE AND RENEWABLE ENERGIES: GLOBAL

Electricity generation by source, World 1990-2019

Source: IEA

INTRODUCTION: CLIMATE CHANGE AND RENEWABLE ENERGIES: GLOBAL

Solar PV electricity generation, World 1990-2019

Source: IEA

INTRODUCTION: SOLAR ENERGY: IMPACTS AND TRADE-OFFS

Fig. 3. The dendrogram of main periods effects based on cluster analysis (Ward's method).

INTRODUCTION: SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE AND PUBLIC PARTICIPATION

- Social acceptance of RE projects is crucial for transition.
- Yet, visual impact → public rejection of RE plans
[land-use changes, perceptions of risk, general NIMBI?]
- Public support → high level awareness to CC, smaller scales of the projects, financial compensation.
- Conceptual and practical history, and also critiques of PP
- Different levels of PP in planning, also as part of SEA or EIA
- One-way information sharing → legitimization

<https://carbon.coop/-ot-tstiv-nuo/2016/09/000c-3grmc-naigch-naillfr-elt-rewopoc>

→ who is consulted and at which stage of the planning process?

LANDSCAPE IMPACT ASSESSMENT (LCA): DEFINITIONS, TOOLS, LIMITATIONS

- **What is landscape?**
 - Diverse meanings in many disciplines
 - Nature-human divide
 - (70s) "landscape ecology" = geomorphological traits + anthropogenic land-uses. Cultural landscapes (UNESCO)
 - (2000) "a zone or area as perceived by local people or visitors, whose visual features and character are the result of the action of natural and/or cultural (that is, human) factors" (European Landscape Convention - ELC)

LANDSCAPE IMPACT ASSESSMENT (LA): DEFINITIONS, TOOLS, LIMITATIONS

- **Procedures of LCAs and limitations**
 - "the process of identifying and describing variation in the character of the landscape. It seeks to identify and explain the unique combination of elements and features (characteristics) that make landscapes distinctive" (LCA, UK)
 - Assess the identity of landscapes considering the specific perceptions and values of the people who experience it
 - A wide range of methods and tools for identifying and analyzing landscape impacts of proposed development projects: EIA, SEA, VIA
 - Assessing aesthetic (sense/judgment of impact) and perceptual (e.g., visibility)
 - Lack of consistency in LA approaches and techniques, and the shortage of data: what exactly do you assess and how

→ The stage during the planning process when the landscape assessment is conducted and who is consulted

LANDSCAPE IMPACT ASSESSMENT (LA): DEFINITIONS, TOOLS, LIMITATIONS

- **Energy landscapes**
 - How society should be dealing with transformations of valued landscapes in the face of the climate crisis?
 - Visual impact is a major impediment to obtaining public consent for RES plans (Scognamiglio, 2016; Wolsink, 2019).
 - Early stages!! Public participation in landscape appraisal and site-selection is considered crucial (Aitken et al., 2016)
 - LAs of RES projects: quantify the visual effects of **shape, color, visibility** and **size** of the facilities in order to define "suitable" constellations of the technology in particular landscapes
 - New cultural features? (Selman, 2010)

METHODOLOGY

- Case-study approach (Israel → *Ashalim* project)
- Extensive documents analysis (planning committees' protocols, policy documents, EIA's official reports, regulation)
- In-depth semi-structured interviews with 11 stakeholders (conducted via phone or zoom): the Ministry of Environmental Protection, the Natural Parks Authority, The Southern District Planning Committee, the regional council, and the Society for Protection of Nature (eNGO)
- Sorting of written materials via coding and thematic analysis

CASE STUDY: BACKGROUND: ISRAEL'S ENERGY GEOGRAPHIES

Share of RE (installed capacity, MW). Source: Electricity Authority, Annual report 2021)

CASE STUDY: BACKGROUND: ISRAEL'S ENERGY GEOGRAPHIES

- Energy island?
- Population: 9.5 million
- Land: 21,937 km²
- Total RES targets 9.8GW (20%) in 2025 and 30% in 2030
- Most available land in the southern regions, but:
 - Population is in center and north
 - Terrain is problematic
 - No grid
 - And...(next slide)

Suitability analysis of land areas for PV facilities. Source: Shriki et al., 2022

CASE STUDY: BACKGROUND: ISRAEL'S ENERGY GEOGRAPHIES

- Population growth rate (highest in OECD)
- Electricity demand growth (scenarios of 2.5-3.7% yearly) – exceeds installed capacities

Source: The Research and Information Center, Israeli Parliament, 2021

TECHNICAL DETAILS

- The largest facility in the country (121MW)
- Concentrating thermal Solar Power (CSP) technology 50,600 computer-controlled heliostats covering an area of 3km² and 240-m-high tower
- Beginning of planning process: 2002
- Facility became operational: 2019
- BOT, national-level planning
- One out of 3 solar fields around *Ashalim*
- Military zone redesignated
- Main EIAs conducted in 2011, 2012

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CASE STUDY: RESULTS

1. Landscape related loopholes in Ashdod planning process

- LA is not a legally binding instrument, but commonly integrated
- This initial choice of site (in 2002) is the most crucial one – no LA, no SEA/EIA
- The EIA and LA for site approval were conducted on a theoretical plan, without knowing the technology of the "tower" (270 m high!)
- No authority is setting standards or overseeing LA procedures
- Landscape considerations "falls between the chairs", considered less of importance compared with ecological damage (streams, wildlife)

CASE STUDY: RESULTS

2. Whose this landscape anyway? Public participation in the project

Ministry of energy, public consultation website, 2016

- No legal requirement for public participation in EIA procedures, only notification
 - The public can file objections, voluntary meetings, organized by the developers
 - Support from the Regional Council, potential of new energy tourism
- The village was compensated with public amenities and only one resident submitted an objection
- Local residents cared more in the planning of electrical substations and high voltage powerlines. This "old" energy landscape involved some negotiation with the local residents who demanded that the stations be positioned as far as possible from the village.

SOME HIGHLIGHTS/CONC.

- "The more important the facility is to the state, the less influence the EIA has..." (regional council representative)
- If LA is so subjective who should be involved in the assessment of impacts?
- Case-by-case vs. spatial policy
- **Length of planning:** the tools for impacts mitigation are not effective and RE goals are missed
- Scenic impacts: in **site selection stage!**
- Landscape has little to say in the case of solar energy
- **LA remains a limited tool:** no post-evaluation of actual impacts

THANK YOU

Na'ama Teschner
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GIS-based multi-Criteria decision analysis for Renewable Energy Systems' site selection, by Eva Loukogeorgaki

An innovative sustainable spatial energy planning framework is developed on national scale for identifying and prioritizing appropriate, technically, and economically feasible, environmentally sustainable as well as socially acceptable sites for the siting of large-scale onshore Wind Farms (WFs) and Photovoltaic Farms (PVFs) in Israel. The proposed holistic framework of this conference consists of distinctive steps allocated in two successive modules (the Planning and the Field Investigation module), and it covers all relevant dimensions of a sustainable siting analysis (economic, social, and environmental). It advances a collaborative and participatory planning approach by combining spatial planning tools (Geographic Information Systems (GIS)) and multi-criteria decision-making methods (e.g., Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP)) with versatile participatory planning techniques to consider the opinion of three different participatory groups (public, experts, and renewable energy planners) within the site-selection processes. Moreover, it facilitates verification of GIS results by conducting appropriate field observations. Sites of high suitability, accepted by all participatory groups and field verified, form the outcome of the proposed framework. The results illustrate the existence of high suitable sites for large-scale WFs' and PVFs' siting and, thus, the potential deployment of such projects towards the fulfillment of the further Israeli energy targets.

PEARLS *Planning & Engagement Arenas for Renewable Energy Landscapes*
 H2020 – MSCA – RISE – 2017 – 778039 *Research Seminar, University of Seville, Seville, Spain, October 26-27, 2022*

GIS – based Multi – Criteria Decision Analysis for Renewable Energy Systems' Site Selection

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 WP4 Leader

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Problem Definition (1)

- **Prerequisite** (at an early stage) for realizing **Renewable Energy Systems (RES) projects**: **Determination of areas suitable** (national, regional etc scale) for the **deployment of the corresponding RES**

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Problem Definition (2)

- **RES site selection**: **Complex, multidimensional decision making process** (joint assessment/management of **conflicting siting criteria** related to **technical, economic, environmental, legal and socio-political factors**)

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Problem Definition (2)

- **RES site selection**: **Complex, multidimensional decision making process** (joint assessment/management of **conflicting siting criteria** related to **technical, economic, environmental, legal and socio-political factors**)

Problem Definition (2)

• *RES site selection: Complex, multidimensional decision making process* (joint assessment/management of *conflicting siting criteria* related to *technical, economic, environmental, legal and socio-political factors*)

Problem Definition (2)

• *RES site selection: Complex, multidimensional decision making process* (joint assessment/management of *conflicting siting criteria* related to *technical, economic, environmental, legal and socio-political factors*)

Analysis Framework (1)

• A *two-stage process* (usually): *Exclusion stage (Stage 1)* & *evaluation stage (Stage 2)*

Analysis Framework (1)

• A *two-stage process* (usually): *Exclusion stage (Stage 1)* & *evaluation stage (Stage 2)*

- PEARLS Research Seminar, October 26-27, 2022
- ### Siting Criteria: General
- **Siting criteria** (exclusion & assessment):
 - **Dependence** upon *RES type* and *study area* (sometimes and upon *data availability*)
 - **Description** of *technical, economic, environmental, legal* and *socio-political factors*
 - **Determination** based on *existing regulation, authorities requirements, experts* (e.g. spatial planners) *knowledge and expertise, best practices, literature, public opinion*

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Siting Criteria: Example of exclusion criteria for onshore wind projects*

Description	Frequency of Occurrence	Mean Value	Min/Max Value	Predominant Value(s)
Urban and residential areas	28	1125 m	0/3000 m	500 m
Protected environmental areas	24	550 m	0/2000 m	0 m
Proximity to road network	23	220 m 6335 m	0/500 m 2000/10,000 m	500 m N/a upper limit (10,000 m)
Civil/military aviation areas	22	4060 m	0/17,000 m	2500 and 3000 m
Slope of terrain	19	18.65%	10/37.2%	10%
Water surfaces	17	475 m	0/4000 m	100 and 400 m
Proximity to high-voltage electricity grid	16	160 m 7400 m	50/250 m 2000/10,000 m	100 and 250 m N/a upper limit (10,000 m)
Bird habitats and migration corridors	16	560 m	0/3000 m	0 m
Archaeological, historical, and cultural heritage sites	14	990 m	0/3000 m	0, 500, and 1000 m
Wind velocity	12	5.20 m/s	4.5 m/s	5 m/s
Agricultural land	9	85 m	0/500 m	0 m
Protected landscapes	7	855 m	0/2000 m	1000 m
Elevation	7	1315 m	200/2000 m	2000 m
Military zones	6	1690 m	0/10,000 m	0 m
Touristic zones	6	750 m	0/1000 m	1000 m

* Spyridonidou S, Vajona DG. Systematic Review of Site-Selection Processes in Onshore and Offshore Wind Energy Research. *Energies*. 2020; 13(2):5906. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13225906>

PEARLS EFFICIENT WIND ENERGY Research Seminar, October 26-27, 2022

Siting Criteria: Example of exclusion criteria for offshore wind projects*

Description	Frequency of Occurrence	Mean Value	Min/Max Value	Predominant Value(s)
Water depth	18	33.5 m 175 m	5/62 m 20/1000 m	- 50 m
Protected environmental areas	18	780 m	0/3000 m	0 m
Verified shipping routes	14	1205 m	0/4800 m	0 m
Wind velocity	13	5.2 m/s	2/7 m/s	6 m/s
Military zones	11	45.45 m	0/500 m	0 m
Landscape protection/visual and acoustic disturbance	10	7335 m	1000/25,000 m	5000 m
Bird habitats and migration corridors	10	1050 m	0/3000 m	0 m
Pipelines and underwater cables	8	160 m	0/500 m	0 m
Proximity to local ports	7	82,145 m	20,000/200,000 m	100,000 m
Geographic boundaries	7	-	TW ¹ /EEZ ²	TW ¹
Other marine uses	7	DO ³	DO ³ /DO ³	DO ³
Fishing areas	6	105 m	0/500 m	0 m
Proximity to high-voltage electricity grid	5	1000 m	100/1000 m	1000 m
Urban and residential areas	4	60,000 m	20,000/100,000 m	-
		1250 m	100/1500 m	-

¹ TW, territorial waters, and EEZ, exclusive economic zone as exclusion limits. ² Depending on marine use.

* Spyridonidou S, Vagiona DG. Systematic Review of Site-Selection Processes in Onshore and Offshore Wind Energy Research. Energies. 2020; 13(2):5906. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13225906>

PEARLS EFFICIENT WIND ENERGY Research Seminar, October 26-27, 2022

Siting Criteria: Example of assessment criteria for onshore wind projects* (1)

Description	Frequency of Occurrence	Mean Weight	Priority Position	Mean Optimal Value(s)	Mean Poor Value(s)
Wind velocity	22	37%	1 st (94.45%)	≥8.47 m/s	≤5.20 m/s
Proximity to road network	22	12%	3 rd and last (35%)	≤955 m	≥6315 m
Proximity to high-voltage electricity grid	20	13%	2 nd (37.5%)	≤1495 m	≥9380 m
Urban and residential areas	17	12%	3 rd (35.70%)	≥4880 m	≤2010 m
Slope of terrain	15	10%	6 th and penultimate (23.1%)	≤3.91%	≥22.90%
Protected environmental areas	11	10%	2 nd and last (50%)	≥1700 m	≤1060 m
Land cover	9	10%	2 nd (37.50%)	No ¹ and/or ² ≥1335 m	Yes ¹ and/or ² ≤935 m
Civil/military aviation areas	8	6%	Last (50%)	≥13,500 m	≤4915 m
Other land uses	7	18.85%	2 nd (33.33%)	Arid land ³	N/a ³
Wind power density	5	25.15%	1 st (75%)	≥350 W/m ²	≤185 W/m ²

¹ No or yes for the presence of vegetation coverage and specific type of forests. ² Distance from forests. ³ Optimal/poor land-use classes. No values applied. ⁴ No, low- or high-agricultural-capacity land, and/or implementation of safety zone of these areas.

* Spyridonidou S, Vagiona DG. Systematic Review of Site-Selection Processes in Onshore and Offshore Wind Energy Research. Energies. 2020; 13(2):5906. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13225906>

PEARLS EFFICIENT WIND ENERGY Research Seminar, October 26-27, 2022

Siting Criteria: Example of assessment criteria for onshore wind projects* (2)

Archeological/historical and cultural heritage sites	5	8.10%	3 rd (75%)	≥1800 m	≤800 m
Elevation	5	7.50%	N/a	≤30 m	≥350 m
Bird habitats and migration corridors	5	5.95%	Last (100%)	≥12,000 m	≤2375 m
Landscape protection	5	8%	N/a	≥4000 m	≤1500 m
Water surfaces	4	5.12%	N/a	≥635 m	≤275 m
Visual impact	4	5.25%	5 th (50%)	N/a	N/a
Areas with possibility of electromagnetic interference	3	N/a	N/a	≥2750 m	≤700 m
Agricultural land	3	4%	N/a	Low/no ⁴ and/or >2000 m	High ⁴ and/or ≤1000 m
Population density	2	10.04%	N/a	N/a	N/a
Electricity demand/consumption	2	12.85%	N/a	>154,440 MWh	≤3620 MWh
Touristic zones	2	6.40%	N/a	≥2200 m	≤800 m
Religious sites	2	N/a	N/a	>500 m	≤400 m
Proximity to coastline	2	N/a	N/a	>3000 m	≤100 m

⁴ No, low- or high-agricultural-capacity land, and/or implementation of safety zone of these areas.

* Spyridonidou S, Vagiona DG. Systematic Review of Site-Selection Processes in Onshore and Offshore Wind Energy Research. Energies. 2020; 13(2):5906. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13225906>

PEARLS EFFICIENT WIND ENERGY Research Seminar, October 26-27, 2022

Siting Criteria: Example of assessment criteria for offshore wind projects*

Description	Frequency of Occurrence	Mean Weight	Priority Position	Mean Optimal Value(s)	Mean Poor Value(s)
Wind velocity	12	28.30%	1 st (77.80%)	≥9.42 m/s	≤6.43 m/s
Water depth	9	16.33%	2 nd (37.50%)	≤42.5 m	≥382 m
Proximity to high-voltage electricity grid	9	14.85%	3 rd and 5 th (25%)	≤18,375 m	≥330,845 m
Protected environmental areas	8	11%	Last (100%)	≥20,835 m	≤9730 m
Proximity to local ports	6	10%	N/a	≥29,375 m	≥15,000 m
Verified shipping routes	6	6.50%	3 rd and last (80%)	>3704 m or low SD ¹	≤1852 m or high SD ¹
Landscape protection/visual and acoustic disturbance	5	11.80%	Penultimate (50%)	≥15,555 m	≤2250 m
Wind energy potential	4	N/a	N/a	>146,029 MWh/year and/or >770 MW	≤30,212 MWh/year and/or ≤20 MW
Fishing habitats/activity and marine species habitats	4	5.20%	N/a	N/a	N/a
Wind power density	3	N/a	N/a	≥975 W/m ²	≤40 W/m ²
Military exercise areas	3	6%	N/a	>40,000 m	≤20,000 m
Population served	3	13.55%	N/a	N/a	N/a
Distance from the shore (for economic purposes)	3	9%	3 rd (60%)	≤25,750 m	≥200,000 m
Bird habitats and migration corridors	2	N/a	N/a	N/a	N/a
Total investment cost	2	15.60%	2 nd (100%)	N/a	N/a

¹ Low or high degree of shipping density (SD)

* Spyridonidou S, Vagiona DG. Systematic Review of Site-Selection Processes in Onshore and Offshore Wind Energy Research. Energies. 2020; 13(2):5906. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13225906>

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Siting Criteria: Example of exclusion/assessment criteria for PVs projects*

Siting Criterion	Siting Aspect	Unsuitable Land Areas
Global Horizontal Irradiance (GHI)	Economic	<1600 kWh/m ² /year
Average Maximum Temperature	Economic/Technical	>40 °C
Sloped Terrain	Economic/Technical	>5%
Elevation	Technical/Environmental	>2000 m
Military Zones	Political	All
Distance from the Existing Road Network	Economic/Technical/Social	≤150 m and >10,000 m
Distance from the Existing Railway Network	Technical/Social	≤150 m
Distance from the Existing High Voltage Electricity Grid	Economic/Technical	≤150 m and >30,000 m
Distance from Land Protected Areas	Environmental	≤500 m (environmental protected areas)
Distance from Civil and Military Aviation Areas	Political/Technical	≤1000 m
Landscape Protection/Visual and Acoustic Disturbance	Social/Legal	<800 m (urban and residential areas)
Distance from Touristic Zones	Social/Economic	<120 m (solitary residences)
Distance from Mineral Extraction Sites/Quarrying	Technical/Restrictive	≤100 m
Distance from Economic Activities	Social/Technical	≤500 m (no buffer from Industrial Zones)
Distance from Archaeological, Historical and Cultural Areas	Social/Political	<1000 m (WHBS)
Distance from Water Areas	Environmental/Social	≤500 m (rest cultural areas)
Distance from Coastline	Environmental/Social	≤100 m
Farm Required Area	Economic	<5,000,000 m ²

* Spyridonidou, S.; Simani, G.; Loukogeorgaki, E.; Vagiona, D.G.; Ulanovsky, H.; Madar, D. Sustainable Spatial Energy Planning of Large-Scale Wind and PV Farms in Israel: A Collaborative and Participatory Planning Approach. *Energies* 2021, 14, 551. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14090551>

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MCDA Methods for RES Siting Problems

- Support decision makers towards the *systematic evaluation and prioritization* of areas for RES deployment
- Assessment of *multiple, quantifiable or non-quantifiable (qualitative), criteria*

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The AHP Method: General (1)

- Decomposition of the problem into a *hierarchy* with *goal* at the *top*, *criteria* at the *intermediate level(s)* & *decision alternatives* at the *bottom*

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The AHP Method: General (2)

- Implementation of *pairwise comparisons* between: (a) *decision alternatives* with *respect* to *each criterion*

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The AHP Method: General (2)

- Implementation of *pairwise comparisons* between: (a) *decision alternatives* with *respect* to *each criterion* and (b) *criteria* with *respect* to the *goal*

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The AHP Method: General (3)

- Quantification of the *advantage* of *one option* *relative* to the *others*: Utilization of a *fundamental nine point's scale* measurement

Intensity of Importance	Definition
1	Equal importance (equally dominant)
2	Weak or Slight
3	Moderate importance (moderately more dominant)
4	Moderate plus
5	Strong importance (strongly more dominant)
6	Strong plus
7	Very strong importance (very strongly more dominant)
8	Very, very strong
9	Extreme importance (extremely more dominant)

Accurate subjective criteria/alternatives weighting!!

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The AHP Method: Steps (1)

Step 1: Implementation of pairwise comparisons (experts groups, stakeholders and/or the public could contribute, especially for assessment criteria comparisons)

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The AHP Method: Steps (1)

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Step 2: Pairwise comparisons at a given level → Creation of the corresponding **judgment matrix A**

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The AHP Method: Steps (1)

Step 1: Implementation of pairwise comparisons (experts groups, stakeholders and/or the public could contribute, especially for assessment criteria comparisons)

Step 2: Pairwise comparisons at a given level → Creation of the corresponding **judgment matrix A**

For example, assuming n **assessment criteria**, **A** (for the criteria with respect to the goal) takes the form:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & \dots & a_{1j} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ a_{i1} & \dots & a_{ij} & \dots & a_{in} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ a_{n1} & \dots & a_{nj} & \dots & a_{nn} \end{pmatrix}$$

a_{ij} : **Importance of criterion i over criterion j with respect to the goal**

Reciprocal judgement:
 $a_{ji} = 1/a_{ij}$ and $a_{ii} = 1$ for $i=j$

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The AHP Method: Steps (2)

For the n **assessment criteria**, **NC** takes the form:

Step 3: Creation of a normalized comparison matrix NC (for each judgment matrix) by dividing each element in the judgement matrix by its column sum

$$NC = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{a_{11}}{\sum_i a_{i1}} & \dots & \frac{a_{1j}}{\sum_i a_{ij}} & \dots & \frac{a_{1n}}{\sum_i a_{in}} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \frac{a_{i1}}{\sum_i a_{i1}} & \dots & \frac{a_{ij}}{\sum_i a_{ij}} & \dots & \frac{a_{in}}{\sum_i a_{in}} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \frac{a_{n1}}{\sum_i a_{i1}} & \dots & \frac{a_{nj}}{\sum_i a_{ij}} & \dots & \frac{a_{nn}}{\sum_i a_{in}} \end{pmatrix}$$

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The AHP Method: Steps (3)

Step 4: Formation of the priority vector w (for each normalized comparison matrix) by computing the average of the elements in each row of the normalized matrix

Priority vector for assessment criteria: Importance of each criterion and influence of each criterion on the overall goal

Priority vector for decision alternatives: Importance of each alternative with respect to each criterion

For the n assessment criteria, w takes the form:

$$w = \begin{pmatrix} w_1 \\ \dots \\ w_i \\ \dots \\ w_n \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{a_{11} + \dots + a_{1j} + \dots + a_{1n}}{\sum_i a_{i1} + \dots + \sum_i a_{ij} + \dots + \sum_i a_{in}} / n \\ \dots \\ \frac{a_{i1} + \dots + a_{ij} + \dots + a_{in}}{\sum_i a_{i1} + \dots + \sum_i a_{ij} + \dots + \sum_i a_{in}} / n \\ \dots \\ \frac{a_{n1} + \dots + a_{nj} + \dots + a_{nn}}{\sum_i a_{i1} + \dots + \sum_i a_{ij} + \dots + \sum_i a_{in}} / n \end{pmatrix}$$

$w_i, i=1, \dots, n$: relative weights of the assessment criteria

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The AHP Method: Steps (4)

Step 5: Check the degree of consistency of each matrix A by calculating the Consistency Index (CI) and the Consistency Ratio (CR)

For the n assessment criteria, we have:

$$CI = \frac{\lambda_{max} - n}{n - 1} \quad \text{and} \quad CR = \frac{CI}{RI}$$

λ_{max} : maximum eigenvalue ($A \times w = \lambda_{max} \times w$)
 RI : random index value depending depends on the matrix size

- CR should be < 0.1
- $CR \geq 0.1$: the matrix is considered inconsistent and judgments should be repeated

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The AHP Method: Steps (5)

Step 6: Formation of the overall priority scale by multiplying local (alternatives') priorities by the priority of the corresponding criterion in the level above and adding

For the n assessment criteria and m alternatives, we have:

	w_1	...	w_j	...	w_n	Overall priority
Alternative 1	w_{11}	...	w_{1j}	...	w_{1n}	$w_{11} * w_1 + \dots + w_{1j} * w_j + \dots + w_{1n} * w_n$
...
Alternative m	w_{m1}	...	w_{mj}	...	w_{mn}	$w_{m1} * w_1 + \dots + w_{mj} * w_j + \dots + w_{mn} * w_n$

Priority vector of Assessment criteria (points to w_1, \dots, w_n)

Priority vector of Alternative 1 (points to w_{11}, \dots, w_{1n})

Priority vector of Alternative m (points to w_{m1}, \dots, w_{mn})

w_{mn} : relative weight of alternative m with respect to the n assessment criterion

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Geographical Information Systems (GIS)

- GIS: Creation, management, analysis, synthesis and mapping of various types of data
- In RES sitting problems:
 - Creation of GIS database for exclusion and assessment criteria
 - Mapping (thematic maps) of exclusion and assessment criteria (spatial data visualization)
 - Contribution to the assessment of the various alternatives (eligible areas) with respect to assessment criteria (support the formation of the corresponding judgment matrices in AHP)
 - Support the participation of public or experts or stakeholders on the importance assessment of criteria and/or of the alternatives with respect to the criteria
 - Visual impact assessment & quantification
 - Alternatives (eligible areas) visualization

Site Selection of HOWiWaES in Greece (application example): General (1)

• Objective: Site selection of Hybrid Offshore Wind and Wave Energy Systems (HOWiWaES) in Greece*

Why HoWiWaES?

Site Selection of HOWiWaES in Greece (application example): General (1)

• Objective: Site selection of Hybrid Offshore Wind and Wave Energy Systems (HOWiWaES) in Greece*

Why HoWiWaES?

- ✓ Rapid development
- ✓ Many large-scale commercial projects

- ✓ One of the most advanced & rapidly developed ocean energy technologies
- X Still many technological barriers to be competitive

Site Selection of HOWiWaES in Greece (application example): General (1)

• Objective: Site selection of Hybrid Offshore Wind and Wave Energy Systems (HOWiWaES) in Greece*

Why HoWiWaES?

- ✓ Rapid development
- ✓ Many large-scale commercial projects

- ✓ One of the most advanced & rapidly developed ocean energy technologies
- X Still many technological barriers to be competitive

Common objective of offshore wind and wave energy sector: Associated costs' reduction

Site Selection of HOWiWaES in Greece (application example): General (2)

• Objective: Site selection of Hybrid Offshore Wind and Wave Energy Systems (HOWiWaES) in Greece

Why HoWiWaES?

HOWiWaES (OWTs with WECs combined in one structure for simultaneous offshore wind and wave energy exploitation):

- ✓ Contribution to costs' reduction
- ✓ Offer of additional advantages (e.g. increased energy yield, smooth and highly available power output, common grid infrastructure etc.)

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Site Selection of HOWiWaES in Greece (application example): Study area

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Site Selection of HOWiWaES in Greece (application example): Methodology

• A two-stage process: Exclusion stage (Stage I) & evaluation stage (Stage II)

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Site Selection of HOWiWaES in Greece (application example): Exclusion criteria of Stage I

GIS deployment

Utilization Restrictions

- MEA: Military Exercise Areas
- AEH: Areas to be licensed for Exploration and Exploitation of Hydrocarbons
- AOREP: Areas where Offshore Renewable Energy Projects are planned to be or have been installed
- MPA: Marine Protected Areas

Economic and Technical Constraints

- WV: Wind Velocity (<6 m/sec)
- WEP: Wave Energy Potential (<5 kW/m)
- WD: Water Depth (>500 m)

Social Implications

- DS: Distance from Shore (<25 km)

Unsuitable areas for HOWiWaES siting in Greece

Accordingly... Eligible areas for HOWiWaES siting in Greece

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Site Selection of HOWiWaES in Greece (application example): Assessment criteria of Stage II

C1: Wind Velocity (WV)*	• WV exceeds the limit of 6 m/sec (larger WV → higher preference)
C2: Wave Energy Potential (WEP)*	• WEP exceeds the limit of 5 kW/m (largest WEP → higher preference)
C3: Water Depth (WD)**	• WD ranges between 0–500 m (technical solutions with reduced construction/operational costs: larger WD → lower preference)
C4: Distance from Shore (DS)**	• DS larger than 25 km (technical solutions with reduced construction /operational costs: larger DS → lower preference)
C5: Connection to Local Electrical Grid (CLEG)*	• Proximity to a local electrical grid with high voltage capacity
C6: Population Served (PS)†	• Corresponding population of regional units that are defined at a mean distance smaller than 100 km from the centroid of an eligible marine area
C7: Shipping Density (SD)‡§	• Qualitative assessment of SD (low, moderate, high)
C8: Distance from Ports (DP)**	• DP ranges between 50-100 km (ports in terms of supporting the installation process: larger DP → lower preference)

• Economic/Technical factors • MCDA method used in Stage II: AHP

• Economic factors • GIS supporting AHP implementation

• Economic/Socio-political factors

• Socio-political factors

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Site Selection of HOWiWaES in Greece (application example): Results of Stage I (5)

and...

Eligible areas (12) for HOWiWaES siting in Greece

- ✓ Offshore areas **West & East of Crete**
- ✓ Offshore areas in a **lengthwise zone from North-central to central Aegean**

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Site Selection of HOWiWaES in Greece (application example): Results of Stage I (6)

Eligible areas (12) for HOWiWaES siting in Greece

Area	Geographical Location	Size (km ²)
A1	North-East (NE) of Skyros	45.77
A2	East-North-East (ENE) of Skyros	457.33
A3	East (E) of Skyros	283.27
A4	South-East (SE) of Skyros	427.7
A5	South-South-East (SSE) of Skyros	113.19
A6	East-South-East (ESE) of Mykonos	516.86
A7	East (E) of Mykonos	59.37
A8	South-East (SE) of Mykonos	212.48
A9	South-East (SE) of Astypatala	192.32
A10	South-West (SW) of Rhodes	86.56
A11	East (E) of Crete	81.32
A12	North-West (NW) of Crete	21.12

Eligible areas determination affected by the existence of very large WDs (> 500 m) → marine areas with a vast wind and wave energy potential excluded due to spatial constraints resulting from very deep water conditions

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Site Selection of HOWiWaES in Greece (application example): Results of Stage II (1)

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8
C1	1	1	3	5	5	5	7	9
C2	1	1	3	5	5	5	7	9
C3	1/3	1/3	1	3	3	3	5	7
C4	1/5	1/5	1/3	1	1/3	1/3	3	3
C5	1/5	1/5	1/3	3	1	3	3	5
C6	1/5	1/5	1/3	3	1/3	1	3	5
C7	1/7	1/7	1/5	1/3	1/3	1/3	1	3
C8	1/9	1/9	1/7	1/3	1/5	1/5	1/3	1

Pairwise comparison of the 8 evaluation criteria with respect to the goal

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Site Selection of HOWiWaES in Greece (application example): Results of Stage II (2)

Relative weights of the 8 evaluation criteria with respect to the goal

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Site Selection of HOWiWaES in Greece (application example): Results of Stage II (3)

	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7	A8	A9	A10	A11	A12	
A1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1/3	1
A2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1/3	1
A3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1/3	1
A4	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1/3	1
A5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1/3	1
A6	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1/3	1
A7	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1/3	1
A8	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1/3	1
A9	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1/3	1
A10	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1/3	1
A11	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	1	3
A12	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1/3	1

Pairwise comparison of the 12 eligible areas with respect to C2 (WEP)

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Site Selection of HOWiWaES in Greece (application example): Results of Stage II (4)

	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7	A8	A9	A10	A11	A12
A1	1	3	1	3	3	3	1	1	3	3	3	3
A2	1/3	1	1/3	1	1	1	1/3	1/3	1	1	1	1
A3	1	3	1	3	3	3	1	1	3	3	3	3
A4	1/3	1	1/3	1	1	1	1/3	1/3	1	1	1	1
A5	1/3	1	1/3	1	1	1	1/3	1/3	1	1	1	1
A6	1/3	1	1/3	1	1	1	1/3	1/3	1	1	1	1
A7	1	3	1	3	3	3	1	1	3	3	3	3
A8	1	3	1	3	3	3	1	1	3	3	3	3
A9	1/3	1	1/3	1	1	1	1/3	1/3	1	1	1	1
A10	1/3	1	1/3	1	1	1	1/3	1/3	1	1	1	1
A11	1/3	1	1/3	1	1	1	1/3	1/3	1	1	1	1
A12	1/3	1	1/3	1	1	1	1/3	1/3	1	1	1	1

Pairwise comparison of the 12 eligible areas with respect to C3 (WD)

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Site Selection of HOWiWaES in Greece (application example): Results of Stage II (6)

Ranking	Decision alternative	Preference percentage (%)
1	A11	16.1
2	A6	10.9
3	A12	9.9
4	A7	9.3
5	A8	9.2
6	A10	8.0
7	A1	7.0
8	A3	6.7
9	A9	6.5
10	A5	5.6
11	A4	5.5
12	A2	5.4

Ranking of the 12 eligible marine areas

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Site Selection of HOWiWaES in Greece (application example): Results of Stage II (7)

Ranking	Decision alternative	Preference percentage (%)
1	A11	16.1
2	A6	10.9
3	A12	9.9
4	A7	9.3
5	A8	9.2
6	A10	8.0
7	A1	7.0
8	A3	6.7
9	A9	6.5
10	A5	5.6
11	A4	5.5
12	A2	5.4

- ✓ Simultaneous existence of the largest wind & wave energy potential
- ✓ Proximity to a high voltage capacity grid
- ✓ Existence of a quite small DS

Ranking of the 12 eligible marine areas

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Site Selection of HOWiWaES in Greece (application example): Results of Stage II (8)

Ranking	Decision alternative	Preference percentage (%)
1	A11	16.1
2	A6	10.9
3	A12	9.9
4	A7	9.3
5	A8	9.2
6	A10	8.0
7	A1	7.0
8	A3	6.7
9	A9	6.5
10	A5	5.6
11	A4	5.5
12	A2	5.4

- ✓ Significant wind & wave energy potential
- ✓ Satisfaction of important economic factors (e.g. DS, WD)

Ranking of the 12 eligible marine areas

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Site Selection of HOWiWaES in Greece (application example): Results of Stage II (9)

Ranking	Decision alternative	Preference percentage (%)
1	A11	16.1
2	A6	10.9
3	A12	9.9
4	A7	9.3
5	A8	9.2
6	A10	8.0
7	A1	7.0
8	A3	6.7
9	A9	6.5
10	A5	5.6
11	A4	5.5
12	A2	5.4

- ✓ Satisfaction of economic/technical (proximity to local grid) & economic/socio-political (population served) factors

Ranking of the 12 eligible marine areas

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What about public (citizens') participation in the decision-making process?

Social accepted – Sustainable solutions

OWF Site Selection in Greece incorporating Public Participation (application example): General (1)

• Objective: Site selection of Offshore Wind Farms (OWFs) in Greece incorporating public participation*

* Loukogeorgaki, E.; Vagiona, D.G.; Lioliou, A. Incorporating Public Participation in Offshore Wind Farm Siting in Greece. Wind 2022, 2, 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.3390/wind2010001>

OWF Site Selection in Greece incorporating Public Participation (application example): Methodology

OWF Site Selection in Greece incorporating Public Participation (application example): Methodology

OWF Site Selection in Greece incorporating Public Participation (application example): Methodology

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OWF Site Selection in Greece incorporating Public Participation (application example): Results of Phase III (2)

Ranking	EMA	Preference percentage (%)
1	EMA11	12.2
2	EMA3	11.3
3	EMA10	11.1
4	EMA4	8.8
5	EMA1	8.7
6	EMA13	7.6
7	EMA5	7.5
8	EMA12	7.1
9	EMA9	6.3
10	EMA7	5.8
11	EMA6	5.7
12	EMA8	4.7
13	EMA2	3.8

Ranking of the 13 EMAs

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OWF Site Selection in Greece incorporating Public Participation (application example): Results of Phase III (2)

Ranking	EMA	Preference percentage (%)
1	EMA11	12.2
2	EMA3	11.3
3	EMA10	11.1
4	EMA4	8.8
5	EMA1	8.7
6	EMA13	7.6
7	EMA5	7.5
8	EMA12	7.1
9	EMA9	6.3
10	EMA7	5.8
11	EMA6	5.7
12	EMA8	4.7
13	EMA2	3.8

- ✓ Large WV (in the range of 6.5-7.5 m/s)
- ✓ Close proximity to local grid of high capacity
- ✓ Potential to serve a large population.

Ranking of the 13 EMAs

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OWF Site Selection in Greece incorporating Public Participation (application example): Sensitivity Analysis (2)

Ranking of the 13 EMAs for the 5 different scenarios

Ranking	EMA (preference percentage)				
	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Scenario 4	Scenario 5
1	EMA11 (12.2%)	EMA11 (12.2%)	EMA11 (12.2%)	EMA11 (12.2%)	EMA10 (12.1%) *
2	EMA3 (11.3%)	EMA10 (11.6%) *	EMA3 (11.3%)	EMA3 (11.2%)	EMA11 (11.3%) *
3	EMA10 (11.1%)	EMA3 (11.5%) *	EMA10 (11.1%)	EMA10 (11.1%)	EMA3 (11.0%) *
4	EMA4 (8.8%)	EMA4 (8.9%)	EMA4 (8.8%)	EMA4 (8.8%)	EMA13 (8.8%) *
5	EMA1 (8.7%)	EMA1 (8.5%)	EMA1 (8.7%)	EMA1 (8.7%)	EMA1 (8.5%)
6	EMA13 (7.6%)	EMA13 (7.3%)	EMA13 (7.5%)	EMA13 (7.5%)	EMA12 (8.3%) *
7	EMA5 (7.5%)	EMA5 (7.2%)	EMA5 (7.4%)	EMA5 (7.4%)	EMA4 (8.3%) *
8	EMA12 (7.1%)	EMA12 (6.8%)	EMA12 (7.0%)	EMA12 (7.1%)	EMA5 (7.3%) *
9	EMA9 (6.3%)	EMA9 (6.4%)	EMA9 (6.3%)	EMA9 (6.3%)	EMA9 (5.8%)
10	EMA7 (5.8%)	EMA7 (5.8%)	EMA7 (5.7%)	EMA7 (5.7%)	EMA6 (5.6%) *
11	EMA6 (5.7%)	EMA6 (5.7%)	EMA6 (5.6%)	EMA6 (5.6%)	EMA7 (5.3%) *
12	EMA8 (4.7%)	EMA8 (4.7%)	EMA8 (4.7%)	EMA8 (4.7%)	EMA8 (4.3%)
13	EMA2 (3.8%)	EMA2 (3.7%)	EMA2 (3.8%)	EMA2 (3.8%)	EMA2 (3.7%)

* Different ranking compared to Scenario 1.

- ✓ Scenarios 3-4: No difference in the ranking compared to baseline scenario
- ✓ Scenario 2: A small change compared to Scenario 1
- ✓ Scenario 5: Differences compared to the baseline scenario

- ✓ **EMA10: 1st place** (one of the most socially accepted areas)
- ✓ **EMAs 12 and 13 : Higher positions** (two of the most socially accepted areas)

PEARLS Research Seminar, October 26-27, 2022

Conclusions

- **RES site selection: Complex, multidimensional decision making process** (joint assessment/management of **conflicting siting criteria** related to **technical, economic, environmental, legal and socio-political factors**)
- **MCDA methods can be efficiently combined with GIS to tackle RES site selection problems**
- **Good & sufficient spatial data are required**
- **Active public and/or stakeholders engagement within the relevant site-selection process may be important (the size of the sample is crucial!!!)**

PEARLS Research Seminar, October 26-27, 2022

Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews

GIS-based multi-criteria decision analysis for site selection of hybrid offshore wind and wave energy systems in Greece

Minasios Tsakalof¹, Eva Loukogeorgaki^{1*}, Dimitris G. Vassilios¹

energies

Site Selection of Hybrid Offshore Wind and Wave Energy Systems in Greece Incorporating Environmental Impact Assessment

Eva Loukogeorgaki¹, Dimitris G. Vassilios^{1*} and Minasios Tsakalof¹

wind

Incorporating Public Participation in Offshore Wind Farm Siting in Greece

Eva Loukogeorgaki¹, Dimitris G. Vassilios^{1*} and Anni Kallianou¹

energies

Sustainable Spatial Energy Planning of Large-Scale Wind and PV Farms in Israel: A Collaborative and Participatory Planning Approach

Yaeli Apstein-Rosen¹, George Tsionas¹, Eva Loukogeorgaki^{1*}, Dimitris G. Vassilios¹, Hani El-Kawas¹ and Shoshan Rubin¹

sustainability

Genetic Algorithms-Based Optimum PV Site Selection Minimizing Visual Disturbance

Nikolaos Nychanidis¹, Eva Loukogeorgaki^{1*} and Michalis Christoussis¹

PEARLS Research Seminar, October 26-27, 2022

EMPOWERING LANDSCAPES

H2020 – MSCA – RISE – 2017 – 778039

Thank you very much for your attention

Transition from research to operations, use of downstream space technologies to ensure nature and climate-positive action, by Betty Charalampopoulou

"Transition from research to operations, use of Downstream Space Technologies to ensure nature and climate-positive action"

Betty Charalampopoulou
Geosystems Hellas S. A.Research Seminar,
Seville
October, 26 -27, 2022

www.geosystems-hellas.gr

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Research Seminar – Seminar on Education – Doctoral Programme in Geography – University of Seville – PEARLS Project – Erasmus+ – Call for Proposals

PLANNING AND ENGAGEMENT ARENAS FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY LANDSCAPES IN SOUTHERN EUROPEAN COUNTRIES & ISRAEL

26 October 2022

16:00 to 16:30 Open lecture A.Lia K – Faculty of Geography and History, University of Seville

16:30-17:00 A place under the sun: planning, landscape, and participation in a case of a solar powerplant in the Israeli desert
Naama Teicher Department of Geography and Environmental Development - Ben-Gurion University of the Negev (Israel)

17:00-17:05 Coffee Break

17:05-18:15 GIS based multi-criteria decision analysis for renewable energy systems' site selection
Siti Calogriou Department of Civil Engineering, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece)

18:15-19:00 Transition from research to operations, use of Downstream Space Technologies to ensure nature and climate-positive action
Betty Charalampopoulou President and CEO in GEOSYSTEMS HELLAS, Athens (Greece)

27 October 2022

16:00 to 16:10 Flashback to Thessaloniki plants Vitis T & Z, 8km, 2004, 09 Vitis (C&A)

PEARLS Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska Curie Grant Agreement No. 778039.

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GEOSYSTEMS HELLAS

- Established in Athens in 2009 as the newest member of GEOSYSTEMS EU GROUP, with shareholder minority on GS GmbH and the rest .
- Nowadays, [GSH] is a Greek SME with a German minority shareholder who was fully acquired from OHB SE on February 2022, so [GSH] is a "sister company" to OHB SE.
- [GSH] has a Dynamic participation to the downstream space sector.
- [GSH] is a funded member of the si-cluster since 2014 (the Unique Hellenic Space Cluster) the Hellenic Association of Space Industry (HASI) and the European Association of Remote Sensing Companies (EARSC) actively participating in the board as the GSH CEO is an elected representative.
- GSH CEO is an EARSC Director and appointed to GEO as the EARSC representative for the Post-2025 Working Group (preparing the Ministerial 2023 and 2015).
- [GSH] participates in ESA and GEO working groups.

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- Serves and consult on services and products to public and private through various industrial projects on
 - ❖ Photogrammetry,
 - ❖ Remote Sensing,
 - ❖ Space & Earth Observation,
 - ❖ GIS,
 - ❖ Imagery intelligence (IMINT)
 - ❖ Geospatial intelligence (GEOINT)
 - ❖ and Smart Cities

- GSH is The Hexagon Geospatial sole reseller and Hexagon Airborne Solutions authorized reseller in Greece and Cyprus
- GSH participates in National and European R&D projects and opportunities on the fields of Environment & Climate Change Adaptation, Urban Resilience & Well-being, Culture Heritage Preservation, Forestry & Agriculture, ICT, and Digital Twin Modelling

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The implementation of the "New space economy"

- **resilience**
 - ✓ Near real time monitoring by Earth Observation technologies
 - ✓ Definition of risks (risks & hazards)
 - ✓ Earth observation and Decision Systems
 - ✓ Smart cities & security / Emerging Technologies and Blockchain
 - ✓ Borders monitoring and EO contribution to DSS
- **adaptation**
 - ✓ Proposals and design
 - ✓ Utilities
 - ✓ Culture Heritage
 - ✓ Biodiversity
- **sustainable development**
 - ✓ Change of urban zone
 - ✓ Design of green structures in the city
 - ✓ NBS & blue and green growth
 - ✓ Citizen health and quality of life
 - ✓ GIS / WebGIS

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- ◊ High-level applications of remote sensing and photogrammetry, in the space sector
- ◊ Software solutions for on-board and on-site atmospheric correction, cloud cover control and generation of high precision cloud mask
- ◊ Management techniques for big data analysis, machine learning techniques (Big Data Analysis, Data Fusion, ML/DL), - System & Software design and development
- ◊ Airborne Lidar 3D monitoring techniques – development of detectable traces methodology
- ◊ Spatial analysis and GIS / WebGIS applications
- ◊ Geospatial intelligence (GEOINT) and data analytics
- ◊ Smart cities and Security – Earth Observation and Blockchain solutions

Recent & Current collaborations on:

- Earth Observation (EO)
- NBS & Blue/Green growth
- Lidar point cloud processing
- Monitoring Cultural Heritage
- Monitoring hazards & Decision Support Systems & Early Warning Systems
- EO application for security

**HORIZON 2020/EUROPE
National R&D projects
National Projects Service Delivery**

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Ongoing R&D projects under the H2020 framework

Ongoing National R&D projects

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**Earth observation based services for renewable energies
(solar, wind, hydro-energy, biomass, geothermal and tidal energy)**

The space industry, and related applications and tools, gives rise to a significant and innovative approach to clean energy generation; it is enough to think that starting from satellite missions, providing more and more accurate weather information from Meteo satellites helping the choice of the installation areas and on wind speed and sun coverage.

Macro level climate changes are impacting potential the renewable energies installations and/or new planned installations.

Large role of EO on biodiversity impact assessment for new sites.

EO satellites could be useful in the pre-feasibility phase to discriminate the type of installation that is not efficient for the selected location. We are able to map every area of the globe pipelines and power lines.

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Space systems can measure the emissions, the wind turbine system is much more efficient than the photovoltaics in terms of financial indicators as well as the annual emission reduction of greenhouse gases.

Proven potential to accelerate businesses and carbon neutral ambitions of large energy companies.

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Outlook

- Earth Observation will play an increasingly large role in:
 - Enabling REPowerEU goals, particularly by playing a role in the identification of 'go-to-areas' for renewable energy sources (wind/solar)
 - Nowcasting of intermittent energy sources power generation (wind/solar) to balance the grid
 - Energy distribution by monitoring critical network infrastructure
 - Third party/independent assessments of Environmental, Social and Governance considerations
 - Need to assess potential of Earth Observation for alternative sources (e.g., hydrogen and biomass)
- Key take-away:
 - Existing data very valuable
 - Awareness raising among users remains important activity to ensure further uptake of EO data-powered services in Energy

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A French start-up has developed a green process to up-cycle raw materials from solar panels. ROSI just won the EU's new Industry of the Future Award...promises to enhance Europe's strategic autonomy by extending the domestic availability of valuable raw materials for industries including solar, electronics and batteries. In reducing industrial waste, the project also helps the European economy to become more sustainable, or "circular".

French tech start-up wins EU's new Industry of the Future Award with raw-materials prowess | Research and Innovation (europa.eu)

Recycling silicon from solar panels advances Europe's green goals as well as creating jobs and harnessing scarce resources.

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May 2016

The magnitude of flood events often overcomes the response capacity of the institutions.

EO product developments have provided enhanced detection capacity in support of such applications.

mapping the flood extent / estimating the number of affected people/operational EO-based flood disaster risk financing

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E65, October 2020

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Multisource survey grade information

- **Imagery**
 1. Stereo Models with photogrammetric exploitation (complimentary information where surface needs to be enhanced with breaklines)
 2. Ortho Imagery with rigorous photogrammetric generation
- **Lidar**
 1. Classified Point clouds (ground, buildings, etc)
 2. Automatic feature extraction and validation for some object classes
- **Fused data (Imagery + LIDAR)**
 1. Attributed color assignment in point clouds

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- Surface generated for all area study.
- Surface had selected critical ground class from Lidar along with critical breaklines

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Classification Methods

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**Sendai Framework
Disaster Risk Reduction**

	Reduce	Increase
7 GLOBAL TARGETS	Mortality/ global population 2020-2030 Average <= 2005-2015 Average	Countries with national & local DRR strategies 2020 Value >> 2015 Value
	Affected people/ global population 2020-2030 Average <= 2005-2015 Average	International cooperation to developing countries 2030 Value >> 2015 Value
	Economic loss/ global GDP 2030 Ratio <= 2015 Ratio	Availability and access to multi-hazard early warning systems & disaster risk information and assessments 2030 Values >> 2015 Values
	Damage to critical infrastructure & disruption of basic services 2030 Values <= 2015 Values	

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**Conclusion
7 Future**

Thank You

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IV. Networking Event

The PEARLS project aims reinforcing participant networks within Mediterranean countries as a way of renewable energy landscapes to be theorized, detected, addressed, and provide crucial support for the Pan-European Energy Challenge. By establishing international, intersectoral and multidisciplinary collaboration the project is building a nexus of a five-country holistic pool of universities and research centers in close cooperation with non-academic sectors. Although the initial idea to organize a Research Seminar after the second half of the project intended to disseminate research project results between PhD students as secondments, after the coronavirus pandemic and international political circumstances the idea has been reformulated. And the Research Seminar has been also considering as a challenge to project implementation, opening to all participants from academic and non-academic sectors to share the consortium's internal network activities.

Project implementation uncertainly due to the spread of coronavirus needs some actions to avoid virtual means of communication. All Work Packages has been and could being affected by this risk because they include secondments, network activities, tasks, and deliverables. First of them cannot be done under remote modes so a set of actions to exchange information, knowledge and innovation must no avoid social events in presential mode. This Networking Event has consisted of a two-hour session aimed at reinforcing communication between the secondments that had travelled to Seville beforehand and those who came expressly to participate in the results of the research seminar. In this way, personal contacts between all of them has been strengthened, helping to bring together perspectives and ways of dealing with future secondments in an atmosphere of collaboration and understanding. At the same time, it has served to encourage those project participants who have not yet implemented secondments to do so by making them understand the map of destinations, the panorama of options for realization and to make sense of the advantages provided by the exchanges.

V. Field work on local case Study

Valle 1 and Valle 2

Location: San José del Valle, Cádiz
Owner: Torresol Engery

Start: 2012

Power: 50 MW each

Electricity generation per year: 160GWh

The Valle 1 and Valle 2 solar thermal plants, in commercial operation since January 2012, are in San José del Valle (Cádiz). They are twin 50 MW adjoining plants¹ owned by Torresol Energy. Both are developed with parabolic trough technology and have a molten salt storage system that allows them to continue producing electricity for 7.5 hours without sun,² i.e. at night or in cloudy weather.

Construction of Valle 1 and Valle 2 began in December 2009 and was completed in December 2011. Around 4,500 workers put in more than 2,700,000 hours of work during the two years of construction and until the plants, which are now connected to the Spanish national grid, were commissioned. Each of the 50 MWe plants can supply 160 GWh of clean and safe energy per year to 40,000 households. Together they reduce CO₂ emissions by more than 90,000 tones per year. Thanks to molten salt storage, which allows the plants to continue producing electricity in the absence of solar radiation, this clean source also becomes manageable, as it can supply the grid according to demand.

Valle 1 and Valle 2 use SENER trough parabolic trough technology, which concentrates solar radiation onto a central collector tube through which thermal oil circulates. In addition, they are equipped with a high-precision optical sensor that tracks the sun from east to west. The hot oil is used to vaporize water which, through expansion in a steam turbine, drives an electric generator that injects the energy into the grid.

Torresol Energy promotes the technological development, construction, operation, and maintenance of large concentrated solar power plants around the world. With the start-up of Valle 1 and Valle 2, the company has already developed three projects, including Gemasolar, which began commercial operation in May 2011.

<https://www.energy.sener/project/valle-1-and-valle-2-plant>

Valle 1 and Valle 2 parabolic trough plants

Valle 1 and Valle 2 parabolic trough plants, San José del Valle, Cádiz, Spain.

Valle 1 and Valle 2 are two adjacent 50 MW plants of electrical energy generation with similar characteristics located in San José del Valle (Cadiz, Spain).

The technology of these two twin plants is the parabolic trough collectors. Each of them consist of a solar field of 510,000 m² of SENERtrough® kind collectors, previously developed and qualified by SENER. These collectors count on a high accuracy optical sensor to follow the sun from East to West to accumulate, this way, the maximum solar radiation.

More than 3,500 h annual production per plant

95,000 t CO₂ emission savings per year

80,000 homes receive this clean and safe power

The net power production for each of the Valle 1 and Valle 2 plants is 160 GWh/year. Thanks to their respective thermal storage systems, with 7,5 hours capacity, both plants will provide energy without fluctuation or interruptions, contributing to the power supply stability for more than 3,500 hours per plant/year, saving emissions of 95,000 t of CO₂ per year. 80,000 homes receive this clean and safe power.

SENER acted as project manager and provided 100% of the technology and engineering for both plants. Valle 1 and Valle 2 were built in parallel, with the logistics this implied: processing various types of supplies (purchasing, manufacturing, inspection, authorization of shipments to the site, transportation, receiving, and on-site storage), overseeing multiple contractors, quality control of the execution and, above all, planning and supervising construction as it progresses. This type of parallel construction has made Valle 1 and Valle 2 a milestone in the solar power industry.

Project data:

- Main characteristics: Parabolic trough and molten salt storage.
- Total mirror surface: 2x510,000 m².
- Number of SCA/loops: 2x624/156 SENERtrough®.
- Field surface area: 2x198 Ha.
- Nominal solar field thermal output: 2x262 MWt.
- Thermal storage capacity: 2x1,010 MWhth (7.5h).
- Turbine capacity: 2x50 MWe.
- Thermal cycle efficiency: 38%.
- Annual normal direct radiation: 2,057 KWh/m²
- Electricity delivery to 80,000 household.
- Around 95,00 tons/year of CO₂ emissions saved.
- Contract type: EPC.
- Scope: Basic Engineering, Detail Engineering Construction, Commissioning and Start-Up.
- Partners: ACS - COBRA.

Client: Torresol Energy
Start date: 2009
Ending date: 2011

VI. References

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